

A STUDY ON CONSUMER PREFERENCE AND MARKET SHARE OF AMUL AND PARAG (MILK AND MILK PRODUCTS) IN SITAPUR DISTRICT OF UTTAR PRADESH

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Abstract:

During the study it has been revealed that in landholding category the maximum farmer was under marginal category followed by small farmer, medium farmer, semi-medium farmer and large farmer. In age category it was found that maximum farmer was in middle age group followed by young age group and old age group. In education category it was found that maximum of respondents was literate and less were illiterate. In gender category it was found that maximum was male followed by female. In category of respondent, it was found that maximum of respondents in General category followed by OBC category and SC/ST category. In family type category it was found that maximum of respondents was living in joint family and less were living in nuclear family. In religion category it was found that maximum were Hindu followed by Muslim and then Christian. Under market share amul is having market share higher than Parag in the study area. Under consumer preference it has been revealed that consumer is preferring amul over parag (milk and milk products) in quality, taste, brand image, availability, packaging quality. But in price category parag is preferred over amul in milk and milk products by respondents in the study area.

Keyword: Chi Square, Consumer Preference and Market Share.

Introduction

Milk is a nutrient-rich liquid produced by the mammary glands of mammals, including cows, goats, and sheep. It contains essential nutrients such as protein, calcium, vitamins, and minerals, making it an important part of a healthy diet. Milk can be consumed in its raw form or used to make a variety of dairy products like cheese, butter, and yogurt. The milk is usually pasteurized, which involves heating it to a high temperature to kill harmful bacteria and extend its shelf life. Packed milk is readily available in various forms and flavors, making it a convenient and popular beverage. However, some individuals may have difficulty digesting lactose, a sugar found in milk. In such cases, alternative dairy-free milk options may be a suitable substitute. Amul and Parag are two popular dairy companies in India that produce a wide range of milk products. Amul produces a variety of dairy products, including milk, butter, cheese, yogurt, and ice cream. Its products are known for their high quality and innovative marketing campaigns. Some of Amul's popular milk products include Amul Gold Full Cream Milk, Amul Taza Double Toned Milk, and Amul Slim & Trim Skimmed Milk. Parag Milk Foods Limited also produces a wide range of dairy products, including milk, cheese, butter, ghee, and paneer. Parag's products are known for their consistent quality and taste. Some of Parag's popular milk products include Gowardhan Fresh Milk, Pride of Cows Milk, and Go Cheese. Both Amul and Parag offer a wide range of milk products to suit different consumer needs and preferences. They are committed to ensuring high-quality and safe dairy products for their customers.

Research Methodology:

Selection of the District:

There are 75 District and 18 division in Uttar Pradesh state Out of these Sitapur district of Uttar Pradesh was selected purposively for the present study on the basis of maximum area under cattle rearing , milk and milk products consumption.

Selection of Block:

There are 23 blocks in Sitapur District. Out of these Khairabad block was selected purposively for the study. The Consumption rate of milk and milk product in this area is high.

Selection of Village:

There are total 114 village in Khairabad block obtained from the block development office. Thereafter these villages was arranged in order on the basis of land holding and consumption of milk and milk products. Thus out of total villages 5% villages were selected randomly for the present study.

Selection of Farmers:

From the selected village list of all crop production farmers and milk and milk consumption respondents was obtained from the block development office in each selected village. Ascending order on the basis of size of their cattle rearing the selection of cultivators from families was listed and 10% farmers was randomly selected from all of the village and then the selected farmers was classified into five sizes of groups.

Table 1: Selection of Respondents:

District	Block	Villages	Respondents					Total
			Marginal	Small	Semi-medium	Medium	Large	
Sitapur	Khairabad	Ahata Kaptan	6	5	5	2	1	19
		Akbar Ganj	7	5	5	4	2	23
		Akbarpur Khurd	3	5	6	5	1	20
		Banehta	7	5	3	6	1	22
		Banka Jalalpur	5	6	4	5	1	21
		Banni Bazar	5	3	2	4	1	15
TOTAL			33	29	25	26	7	120

Analytical Tools

$$m = \frac{\text{sum of the terms}}{\text{number of terms}}$$

Chi Square

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i}$$

Mean

Likert scale:

The Likert scale is a standard classification format for studies. The respondents provide their opinion (data) about the quality of a

product/service from high to low or better to worse using two, four, five, or seven levels.

Result And Discussion

Table 2: Distribution of farmer according to farm size

S. No.	Categories(members)	Respondent	
		Frequency	Percentage
1.	Marginal (< 1 hectare)	33	27.5
2.	Small Farmers (1-2 hectare)	29	24.16
3.	Semi Medium Farmer(2-4)	25	20.83
4.	Medium Farmers (4-10hectare)	26	21.66
5.	Large Farmers (Above 10 hectare)	7	5.84
	Total	120	100

Table 2: reveals Farm size is one of the prime socio-demographic variables in this study. As farm size affects the buying decision, it has an essential association in market-related research. Due to the distinction in their perception and socialization, farm size tend to have distinct conclusions while buying. Out of the total, 120

respondents 33 respondents were having marginal size farm, 29 were having small size farm, 25 were having semi medium size farm, 26 were having medium size farm and remaining 7 were having large size farm.

Table 3: Distribution of respondents based on their ag

S. No.	Categories	Respondent Number	Respondents					Percentage
			Marginal	Small	Semi medium	Medium	Large	
1.	Young agegroup (20-35 years)	36	10	10	5	7	4	30
2.	Middle agegroup(36-50 years)	64	14	15	17	16	2	53.34
3.	Old age group (Above 50 years)	20	9	4	3	3	1	16.67
	Total	120	33	29	25	26	7	100

Table 3: reveals that One of the critical socio-demographic factors in this study is Age. Age is given such importance in market-related research, because it affects the physical and psychological aspect of the consumer, which, in turn, affects his/her buying behavior. From this Table it can be concluded that 36(30%) respondents are in the

young age group of 20-35, 64(53.34%) respondents are in the middle age group of 36-50, 20 (16.67%) respondent are in old age of above 50. Therefore, the majority of respondents are in the middle age group of 36- 50.

Table 4: Distribution of respondents based on their education

S. No.	Categories	Respondents Number	Respondents					percentage
			Marginal	Small	Semi medium	Medium	Large	
1	Primary School	25	13	4	3	4	1	20.83
2	Junior High School	20	5	2	3	9	1	16.66
3	High School	17	4	3	3	6	1	14.16
4	Intermediate	16	1	6	4	4	1	13.33
5	Graduate	12	1	2	7	1	1	10
A	Total Literate	90	24	17	20	24	5	75
6	Illiterate	30	9	12	5	2	2	25
	Total	120	33	29	25	26	7	100

Table 4: Reveals that another socio-demographic factor considered in this consumer behavior study is education. From the table below among 120 respondents, 30(25%) respondents found to be illiterate. The highest number of respondents were found that had studied till primary school that is 25(20.83%), followed by 20(16.66%)

respondents were studied till junior high school, followed by 17(14.16%) had studied till high school, followed by 16(13.33%) had studied till intermediate, followed by 12(10%) had studied till graduation. Thus it can be concluded that total literate found during the study is 90(75%).

Table 5 : Distribution of respondents according to their Gender.

S. No.	Category	Respondents number	Respondents					Percentage
			marginal	small	Semi medium	medium	large	
1	Male	95	28	24	20	20	3	79.16
2	Female	25	5	5	5	6	4	20.83
	Total	120	33	29	25	26	7	100

Table 5: represents Gender is one of the prime socio-demographic variables in this study. As gender affects the buying decision, it has an essential association in market-related research. Due to the distinction in their perception and socialization, men and females tend to have distinct conclusions while buying. Out of the total, 120 respondents 95 respondents were male, that is 79.16% while the remaining 25 were female that is 20.83% of total sample.

Table 6: Distribution of respondents according to their Caste Category.

S. No.	Category	Respondents number	Respondents					Percentage
			Marginal	Small	Semi Medium	Medium	Large	
1	General	58	15	13	11	15	4	48.33
2	OBC	40	9	12	10	7	2	33.33
3	SC/ST	22	9	4	4	4	1	18.33
Total		120	33	29	25	26	7	100

Table 6: Reveals that Caste Category is one of the prime socio-demographic variables in this study. As caste affects the buying decision, it has an essential association in market-related research. Due to the distinction in their perception and socialization, Caste

Category tend to have distinct conclusions while buying. Out of the total, 120 respondents 58 respondents were belonging to general category that is 48.33%, followed by 40 where OBC that is 33.33% while the remaining 22 were SC/ST that is 28.33% of total sample.

Table 7: Distribution of respondents according to their Family type.

S. No.	Category	Respondents number	Respondents					Percentage
			marginal	small	Semi medium	medium	large	
1	Joint	100	31	27	19	20	3	83.33
2	Nuclear	20	2	2	6	6	4	16.66
Total		120	33	29	25	26	7	100

Table 7: reveals that is one of the Family type socio-demographic variables in this study. Asfamily affects the buying decision, it has an essential association in market-related research. Due to the distinction in their perception and socialization, joint family and nuclear family

tendto have distinct conclusions while buying. Out of the total, 120 respondents 100 respondents were male, that is 83.33% while the Remaining 20 were having nuclear family that is 16.66%of total sample.

Table 8: Distribution of respondents according to their religion

S. No.	Category	Respondents number	Respondents					Percentage
			marginal	small	Semi medium	medium	large	
1	Hindu	60	15	12	16	13	4	50
2	Muslim	50	15	14	7	12	2	41.66
3	Christian	10	3	3	2	1	1	8.34
Total		120	33	29	25	26	7	100

Table 8: Reveals that Religion is one of the prime socio-demographic variables in this study.As religion affects the buying decision, it has an essential association in market-related research. Due to the distinction in their perception and socialization, relation tend to have

distinct conclusions while buying. Out of the total, 120 respondents 60 respondents were Hindu, that is 50%, 50 of them belongs to Muslim that is 41.66 % while the remaining 10 were Christian that is 8.34% of total sample.

Table 9: Market Share of Amul and Parag milk Products.

Sr. No.	Particulars	Respondents	
		AMUL Milk & MilkProducts	PARAG Milk AndMilk Products
1	Taste	16	5
2	Shelf life	20	10
3.	Varieties ofproducts	15	11
4.	Price	14	20
5.	Quality	10	5
6.	Availability insmall packs	40	34
		105	85

Table 9: During the Comparative study between amul and parag milk and milk products. Reveals that market share of Amul and parag milk and milk product in segment in the study area. In the above table it has been revealed that market share of AMUL is higher as compared to Parag in study area. In the study area total 105 respondents response out of 120 respondents over the AMUL under various categories taste

16, shelf life 20, varieties of products 15, Price14, Quality 10 and Availability in small packs 40 and in Parag 85 respondents response out of120 respondents under various categories, Taste 5, shelf life 10, Varieties of products 11, Price20, Quality 5, Availability in small packs 34. Thus it can be concluded that AMUL is having highest market share in compared to Parag in the study area.

Table 10: Consumer preference on Quality between Amul milk and milk products and Paragmilk and milk products.

General	Categories	Amul (Milk and Milkproducts)	Parag (Milk and Milkproducts)
Quality	Good	65	50
	Average	45	33
	Poor	10	37
Total		120	120

Table 10: Reveals the consumer preference on the quality between amul (milk and milk products) and parag (milk and milk products). In

Amul 65 respondents' response that quality of amul (milk and milk products) is good, followed by response over average is 45 on the

quality of amul (milk and milk products) and lastly 10 respondents' response over the poor quality of amul (milk and milk products). In Parag 50 respondents response that quality of parag (milk and milk products) is good, followed by response over average is 33 on the

Table 11: Consumer preference on price between Amul milk and milk products and Parag milk and milk products.

General	Categories	Amul (milk and milk products)	Parag (milk and milk products)
Price	Low	16	30
	Medium	27	35
	High	77	55
Total		120	120

Table 11: Reveals the consumer preference on price between Amul (milk and milk products) and Parag (milk and milk products). 16 respondents response on the low price of amul (milk and milk products), where 30 respondents response on the low price of Parag (milk and milk products), 27 respondents response that the price of amul (milk and milk products) is average where under parag (milk and

quality of parag (milk and milk products) and lastly 37 respondents response over the poor quality of parag (milk and milk products). Thus it can be concluded that consumer were preferring amul (milk and milk products) over the Parag (milk and milk products).

milk products) 35 respondents response over the average price. 77 respondents response that price of Amul (milk and milk products) is high where in parag 55 respondents response that price of Parag (milk and milk products) is high. Thus it can be concluded that in price consumer prefers the parag milk and milk products over the amul milk and milk products.

Table 12: Consumer preference on availability between Amul milk and milk products and Parag milk and milk products.

General	Categories	Amul (milk and milk products)	Parag (milk and milk products)
Availability	Retailer shop	45	67
	In smaller pack	57	43
	Varieties	18	10
Total		120	120

Table 12: Reveals the consumer preference on availability between Amul (milk and milk products) and Parag (milk and milk products). 45 respondents response that availability of amul (milk and milk products) over retailer shop where 67 respondents response that availability of parag (milk and milk products). 57 respondents that

availability of amul milk and milk products in small packs where 43 respondents response that availability of parag milk and milk products in small packs. 18 respondents response that there is varieties of products of amul product and milk, where 10 respondents response over the varieties of products of parag milk and milk products.

Table 13: Consumer preference on brand image, taste, packaging between Amul milk and milk products and Parag milk and milk products.

Sr. No.	Categories	Amul (milk and milk products)	Parag (milk and milk products)	Total respondents
1	Brand Image	80	40	120
2	Taste	85	35	120
3	Packaging quality	90	30	120

Table 13: reveals consumer preference on brand image that 80 respondents response out of total sample over brand image of Amul where 40 respondents response on the parag brand image. In Taste category 85 respondents response on the amul (milk and milk products) where 35 respondents response on the parag (milk and milk products). In Packaging quality 90 respondents response on the packaging quality of amul (milk and milk products) where 30 respondents response on the packaging quality of parag (milk and milk products).

Conclusion:

In conclusion, marketing of milk and milk products can be a challenging task for companies operating in this industry. With increasing competition, changing consumer preferences, price fluctuations, distribution challenges, and regulatory compliance, companies need to constantly innovate and adapt to stay ahead in the market. However, the dairy industry also presents several opportunities for growth, particularly with the rising demand for organic, natural, and healthy food products. Companies that can successfully navigate these challenges and capitalize on these opportunities are likely to be successful in the long run. Overall, effective marketing strategies that take into account the unique

challenges and opportunities of the dairy industry can help companies build strong brands and achieve sustainable growth.

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